

**TRADE ACTIVITY OF THE ENTERPRISE AS LOGISTICS AND
MARKETING RELATIONS****Razakov Babirmirza Ramazan ugli**

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In a broad sense, sales management can be interpreted as continuous management of the company's sales. In a narrow sense, sales management means sales planning and actual day-to-day management of the company. Sales management should be carried out as one of the many active functions of the firm and, according to the approved project, is an integral part of marketing, which in turn is part of the joint intention of the firm.

Channel members have implemented a number of functions that contribute to the successful performance of advertising tasks. These include: conducting research and development, conducting advertising, establishing relationships with potential customers, creating products according to customer requirements, transporting and storing products, financing issues, taking responsibility for the performance of the implemented channel.

The main management functions performed in the practice of the marketing system management process are as follows: market segmentation and advertising planning results research; tightening contracts with buyers or intermediaries; taking into account and monitoring the execution of contracts; developing the intention to ship the product to customers; identification of sales channels; organizing the method of product storage, packaging, sorting and shipping to customers; providing information, resources and technical assistance in the resale of goods; sales promotion; establish and arrange a negotiable association with buyers.

Stages of sales management:

1. The definition of channels has been implemented.
2. Selection of mediators.
3. Delivery arrangement.
4. Stimulation of the energy of mediators.
5. Controlling the work of mediators.

The choice of a specific channel to be implemented depends on the characteristics of the planned sales and the firm's preferences, available resources and positioning strategy. If the firm is willing to sacrifice short-term profits to strengthen and expand its position in the market, but direct selling leads to high fixed costs, then personal selling is aimed at expanding its forces. draws a conclusion about. Reselling products through distributors has the lowest fixed costs but the highest variable costs. If the company is established by a small part of the market, it follows the path of solving the proposals of intermediaries.

Since direct implementation is costly, the choice of implementation channel depends on the firm's resources. The choice of channels depends on the positioning strategy. In particular, the issue of the intensity of geographical coverage has a special meaning.

When choosing channels, special attention is paid to the fulfillment of strategic tasks, in particular: market sectors in which the supplier plans to work; some great qualities you want to do.

Having decided on the total number of mediators, it is necessary to determine their type. To do this, you need to study the outstanding qualities and shortcomings of any intermediaries related to the main tasks of the company in the field of distribution.

Members of the distribution network must be motivated to sell the supplier's products effectively. There are motivational and cofactors of motivation. Host channel member incentives include short-term financial "incentives" that encourage resellers to promote a manufacturer's product. A push strategy is important to ensure interaction with advertisers so that the company does not expire in the market.

Controlling the work of channel members by the manufacturer allows to direct it to the interests of the supplier, or at least to have a significant influence on it. The level of control depends on consistent performance goals: sales volume, inventory values, delivery times and customer support, implemented incentives and employee learning programs. Current indicators are periodically compared with benchmarks, differences are identified and appropriate measures are taken.

Sales organization is based on advertising research, which is the basis of all advertising work. These studies in the field of trade consist of studying the need and demand for these products, studying the market capacity, determining the share of the company in the total sales of the presented assortment, analyzing the market situation and analyzing the market characteristics. studying the possibility of entering the foreign market, studying the dynamics of sales, conducting test channels, studying the concept of customers and consumer preferences.

The organization of sales "by function" means the same attitude to foreign markets, for example, to manufactured products, guaranteeing the company special departments with the amount of sales management.

The organization "on the appearance of goods" urgently requires clear criteria for the production, sale and service of all types of products. He creates groups of workers who hunt for "his" product. An active sales service is formed for a specific product. This ensures that all the nuances of marketing are given due attention.

"By Markets" organization requires specific knowledge of customer service in specific sectors or sectors of the economy. It distinguishes groups of employees who deal with "their" group of customers.

Organization "by regions" allows to take into account the characteristics of the use of products in any area with similar demographic and cultural characteristics.

In enterprises, the design of the sales service should be consistent with the advertising strategy. It depends on the concentration (scale) and specialization of production, the territorial location of the company and the value of home independence of its divisions, the individuality of production, the purpose of production, personal (short-term or long-term) value. use create according to the nature and criteria of the company.

The design of the sales service includes both management and, for example, production departments. Management units include sales departments (groups, bureaus). The respective bureaus (groups, sectors) have all the opportunities to enter the sales department: applications, claims research, planning, merchandising (operational), contract requests, export, advertising, delivery, installation, commissioning, delivery service, etc. adding finished products. workshops (departments) for the collection, storage and packaging of products, finished products, packaging, shipping and dispatch.

The content of the advertising functions of finished products includes 3 directions: planning (forecasting), company, control and coordination. Any direction is produced from a series of functions corresponding to the specific characteristics of this direction.

Trade planning includes: study of external and internal conditions; setting goals; development of market and demand monitoring; preparation of monitoring for resale of goods; formation of intentions to deliver finished products; planning appropriate financial relationships; selection of channels of goods; planning of additional offers, foreign economic activities, marketing activities; preparation of estimates for sales and distribution management, profitability planning.

The sales organization includes: a demand intelligence company; tightening housing contracts with buyers for product delivery; choosing forms and methods of product implementation, methods of delivering it to the consumer; preparing the product for shipment to the consumer; development of product distribution; organization of information-dispatch service, reporting; organization of trade relations, legal and judicial practice; demand stimulation and organization of marketing work.

Control and coordination of the work of the sales service includes: assessment of the ratio of the implementation of advertising functions to the program of advertising research; testing the work of the sales service, as well as measures to coordinate the work of the sales service and increase its efficiency; monitoring and evaluation of promotion and marketing activities; sneaky control; control of product delivery, execution of foreign trade operations, fulfillment of contractual promises, actual payment of invoices; correcting the production program according to received orders; Litigation against buyers for breach of contractual promises and late payments.

Difficulties related to the sale of products are identified, goals are set, and their achievement contributes to their conclusion. These goals have all the possibilities to be: to achieve a certain amount of income, sales volume, market share and wholesale turnover by assortment; establish appropriate financial relationships; increase the efficiency of sales staff; optimization of stocks of finished goods; effectiveness of additional offers provided to the consumer; trade rationalization; improving the efficiency of court cases; selection of appropriate channels for sold products; minimization of transport costs; optimization of all types of sales costs; increase the profitability of the enterprise's foreign trade operations; strengthen the implementation of the company's marketing policy; start consumer demand.

The list of goals can be different in different companies and in different periods of the same company. The importance of the listed tasks and goals of the advertising work, that is, the depth of the research, will depend on the criteria it works on.

The development of demand and market monitoring is the basis for the creation of product sales monitoring, which is the basis for all paid transactions in the forecast period, and is the basis for creating current sales intentions and income.

Then, setting tasks and specific goals is governed by the ways, limits and sequence of actions to achieve them, i.e. a project (program) is being developed for sales service work. The inclusion of certain departments in the project is based on the defined tasks.

Sales management should be carried out in accordance with the totality of market and production moments of the company. Without this account, the trading system will conflict with the advertising strategy.

It is in the trading system that the result of all work is concentrated, as a result of which a well-thought-out and well-calculated strategy has the ability to fail if the trading system does not meet the set goals.

The life of the distribution channel implies the distribution of functions and flows between the members of the exchange. The main question in the network is not whether these functions and jets should exist, but which of the channel members must perform them. A great variety can be seen in the spread of functions not only for different markets, but also within market 1. It is important to choose a market coverage strategy when developing the company's sales management methods:

1. An intensive advertising strategy with the introduction of high-probability retail outlets and warehouses. This distribution strategy is suitable for ethnic products, products and non-labor intensive offerings. Features: different profitability of products in the markets; it is not easy to control the entire market; Brand clothing is not easy to maintain.

2. Selective advertising strategy applied to pre-selected products (when the customer conducts marketing of product markets by studying and comparing the property, cost and other characteristics of the product). Features: the manufacturer deliberately limits the availability of products in order to reduce the losses incurred and the benefits of effective cooperation of intermediaries; low product availability leads to loss of customers; often a short indirect channel is implemented and performs the functions of a wholesaler autonomously.

Exclusive distribution and franchising is a way for the producer to borrow the market through only 1 trader (firm). In which product category the marketer must sell to the manufacturer's policy to avoid selling competing brands. Franchising is a vertical contractual advertising system for the sale of products and offers for ethnic use, which provides a long-term contractual relationship between the manufacturer and the company that sells the product on a limited plot of land (franchisor).

Thus, the content of sales management includes the correct directions: planning (forecasting), organization, implemented promotion, control and coordination. Any direction consists of a number of functions that correspond to the specific characteristics of the presented direction, carry a specific methodological load and pursue their own goals.

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